

Finding related documents through family searching

Lars Lundberg¹

¹ lars.lundberg@bth.se

Department of Computer Science, Blekinge Institute of Technology, 371 79 Karlskrona (Sweden)

Introduction

In many cases, e.g., when performing systematic literature reviews, one need to find documents related to a certain document or to a certain set of documents. Historically, traditional database searches based on keywords has been the main way of doing this. For a number of years these traditional search methods have been complemented with so called snowballing. Backward snowballing starting from a document A means that we look at the (older) documents that are cited by A, and forward snowballing means that we look at (newer) documents that cite A. Snowballing and traditional database searches can also be combined in hybrid search strategies (Wohlin *et al* 2022).

Here we define a way to generalize snowballing, to something we refer to as family searching. Compared to traditional backward and forward snowballing there are two clear advantages with family searching: (i) family searches find a larger number of related documents compared to backward and forward snowballing, and (ii) family searches rank the related documents based on how closely related to the starting document (or set of documents) they are.

Family Searching

If document A cites document B one can say that B is a parent of A and that A is a child of B (if A cites B, then A is in some sense at least partly based on B). Obviously, a document can have many parents and children. Using the parent-child metaphor it is also possible to define siblings, i.e., documents that share one or more parents, and partners, i.e., documents that share one or more children. This means that it is possible to define a family of documents that are related to a certain document A. Two documents A and B can be related in different ways. Due to normal chronology, we have the restriction that if B is a parent of A, then A cannot be a parent of B. However, if B is a parent of A, then A and B can also be both siblings and partners. If we define three types of relations between two documents: Parent-Child relation, Sibling relation and Partner relation, then there are in general $2^3 = 8$ different kind of family ties between two documents: (i) no family ties at all, (ii) a Parent-Child relation, (iii) a Sibling relation, (iv) a Parent-Child and a Sibling relation, (v) a Partner relation, (vi) a Parent-Child and Partner relation, (vii) a Sibling and a

Partner relation, and (viii) a Parent-Child, Sibling and Partner relation.

The Parent-Child relation is binary, i.e., either B is a parent of A or it is not a parent of A. The Sibling and Partner relations are, however, not binary. Two documents A and B can have many parents in common and they can also have many children in common. This means that the strength of the Sibling or Partner relation between documents A and B can vary. Clearly, 10 parents in common is a stronger Sibling relation than just having one parent in common.

This means that the family relation between two documents can take many forms. In addition to the eight possible combinations mentioned earlier, the Sibling and Partner relations can have different strengths.

In a family search starting from document A all the documents that have a Parent-Child, Sibling or Partner relation to A are listed. This set of documents is a superset of the set of documents listed by backward and forward snowballing, thus obtaining the first advantage mentioned at the end of the Introduction. In order to obtain the second advantage mentioned at the end of the Introduction, we need to quantify the strength of the family tie between documents A and B.

It is not obvious how the strength of the family tie between two documents should be calculated, and this is something that needs further research. However, one reasonable starting point is to say that a Parent-Child relation is probably stronger than a Sibling or Partner relation, and that a Sibling relation is approximately as strong as a Partner relation. As discussed above a Sibling relation is stronger if the two documents share many parents in common, and a Partner relation is stronger if the two documents share many children in common. However, having ten parents in common does probably not create a family tie that is ten times stronger than the family tie between two documents that only have one common parent. If we think of the strength of a Sibling (or Partner) tie as a function of the number of common parents (or children), then based on the discussion above it is clear that this function should be increasing and have a negative second derivative. Also, even a large number of common parents (or children) does probably not create a family tie that is stronger than the tie between a parent and a child. All these aspects are taken into consideration in the

following definition of a function for the family tie between documents X and Y.

$$\text{FamilyTie}(X,Y) = \text{Parent-Child}(X,Y) + \sum_{i=1}^{\text{CommonParents}(X,Y)} \frac{1}{2^i} + \sum_{i=1}^{\text{CommonChildren}(X,Y)} \frac{1}{2^i},$$

where

Parent-Child(X,Y) equals one if X is a parent of Y or Y is a parent of X, otherwise Parent-Child(X,Y) equals zero.

CommonParents(X,Y) is the number of parents in common for X and Y.

CommonChildren(X,Y) is the number of children in common for X and Y.

From the definition of the FamilyTie-function it is clear that the family tie between two documents is a value that is greater than or equal to zero and smaller than three (if the CommonParents- and CommonChildren-functions return very large values, each of the two sums in the definition of the function FamilyTie will be almost one, as defined by the rules for sums of geometric series).

Figure 1 shows a small example with five documents. In this case $\text{FamilyTie}(B,C) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{2} = 2.25$, since $\text{Parent-Child}(B,C) = 1$, $\text{CommonParents}(B,C) = 2$, and $\text{CommonChildren}(B,C) = 1$. In the example in Figure 1 we also have $\text{FamilyTie}(D,E) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} = 0.75$.

The definition of the function FamilyTie makes it possible to list related documents in an order based on the value of their family ties. For instance, if we would list the documents related to document C in Figure 1 we get the follow order (the value of the family tie in brackets): B (2.25), D (1.5), E (1.5) and A (1). This example demonstrates the second advantage of family searching mentioned at the end of the Introduction.

Figure 1. The relation between five documents (A, B, C, D and E). An arrow indicates that the document from which the arrow starts cites the document that the arrow points to.

Discussion

We have defined three kinds of relations between documents: Parent-Child, Sibling and Partner relations. Backward and forward snowballing only

consider the Parent-Child relation. Family searching based on the function FamilyTie is a generalization of the snowballing approach, since also the Sibling and Partner relations are considered. The Sibling and Partner relations differ from the Parent-Child relation since two documents may share many parents, making the Sibling relation stronger. Similarly, two documents may share many children, making their Partner relation stronger.

In the definition of the function FamilyTie we have tried to condense the three relations into one single value (that is smaller than three and larger than or equal to zero). The idea is that this will capture the ties between two documents in a way that reflects the opinions of the researchers looking for related documents. Initial discussion with researchers in computer science indicate that this way of ranking the related documents seems reasonable and useful. However, a lot of research and testing obviously remain before a final version of the FamilyTie-function can be defined.

It is obviously possible to extend the family tie concept also to cousins, grand parents etc. However, the three relations discussed here are probably the most important ones. Also, going very far out in the family tree will increase the time and processing power needed to perform a family search.

Next Step

We plan to develop a tool that, based on the Scopus database and its API (Rose & Kitchin 2019), will implement the FamilyTie-function. This tool will then be tested on researchers and students. In particular the FamilyTie values calculated by the tool will be compared to a manual ranking of related articles. This manual ranking will be done by students and researcher in computer science and related areas.

References

- Rose, M. E. & Kitchin, J. R. (2019). Pybliometrics: Scriptable bibliometrics using a Python interface to Scopus, *SoftwareX*, vol. 10.
- Wohlin, C., Kalinowski, M., Romero Felizardo, K. & Mendes E. (2022). Successful combination of database search and snowballing for identification of primary studies in systematic literature studies. *Information and Software Technology*, 147, 106908, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2022.106908>